

EDITORIAL NOTE

This is a special, final edition of the Irish Polish Society Yearbook presented to the reader in an annual format. It contains the summary of IPS activities in the year 2014/2015, IPS documents and correspondence, a Photo Album and a selection of papers in English and in Polish.

For the Polish community in Ireland 2015 was the year of a very special occasion, the unveiling of the plaque to Sir Paul Edmund Strzelecki, famous Polish traveller and explorer, whose philanthropy during the Irish Famine had hitherto been almost forgotten. The celebration which took place in Sackville Pl. in Dublin, with the presence of the prominent members of the Irish Government, Polish and Irish Diplomatic Corps, Lord Mayor of Dublin and Mayor of Poznan, and the representatives of the Polish organisations from Ireland, Australia and Poland, marked the ending of the first Polish–Irish Cultural Festival Polska Éire 2015. Detailed information about both events and Strzelecki himself can be found in Hanna Dowling’s two articles and the secretary’s report in the Yearbook (see. *Paul Edmund Strzelecki. His Life, Travels, Discoveries and Humanitarian Work in Ireland; Brian Friel in Poland and Strzelecki Commemorative Plaque in Dublin*).

The articles section in the Yearbook also provides a celebration of another historical event on Irish soil. The year 2016, when this Yearbook was printed, marked the Centenary of the Easter Rising. The significance of the Irish Rebellion of 1916 goes far beyond the military operation. Even if it was on a relatively small scale compared to WWI it is considered to be a stepping stone to the Irish statehood. This was yet another occasion for finding the Polish traces by Patrick Quigley who brought it to light in his article *On Opposite Sides: Casimir & Constance Markievicz in 1916*. Some less known historic facts from the aftermath of the Rebellion from the legal perspective were presented by Maciej Furtas in *Revenge or Justice? The British Military Courts after Easter Rising 1916*. More

legal and historical material was published by Izabela Jankowska – Prochot in *The Foundation of An Garda Síochána. Historical and Legal Study*. Finally Agnieszka Peđrak shared with the readers *The changing nature of the Polish community in Great Britain and Ireland: past and present motivation to emigrate* and Agnieszka Wieczorkowska made an interesting comparison between *Disability in Ireland and in Poland*.

The Reviews section contribution to the Yearbook 2016 are some critical conclusions based on the latest publications of Patrick Quigley's *Sisters against the Empire. Countess Constance Markievicz and Eva Gore-Booth, 1916–17*, Lauren Arrington's *Revolutionary Lives Constance and Casimir Markievicz*, Krzysztof Marchlewicz and Adam Kucharski's *Polska Irlandia wspólna historia: Poland & Ireland – A Common History?* and Gerard Keown, currently serving as Ireland's Ambassador to Poland, *First of the Small Nations: the Beginnings of Irish Foreign Policy in the Interwar Years, 1919–1932*.

This Edition of the IPSY has a unique selection of documents and correspondence between the IPS and various Polish and Irish institutions chosen by Edyta Dolan. Some number of letters and notes initiating the Strzelecki project were also presented in the previous, second Edition of the Yearbook 2015. The excellent photographic material provided mainly by Jason Dolan completed and highlighted these special moments.

Copies of the Irish Polish Society Yearbooks are available in major public and University Libraries in Ireland, University Libraries in Oxford and Cambridge, as well as the National Libraries of Wales and Scotland. The third volume of the Yearbook completes the first of Irish Polish Society serial publications. As it was suggested by the IPS Committee and the IPSY Editorial Advisory Panel the idea of a new journal is to broaden the scope, the timeframe and the range of the next editions. Now when the Irish Polish Society is a leading, recognizable voice within the Polish community in Ireland, manages large and complicated projects and has international contacts on the level of government and non-governmental organisations, this postulate seems to be particularly understandable.

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